

THE IMPACT OF MULTI-SENSORY LANGUAGE TEACHING METHOD ON YOUNG ENGLISH LEARNERS' SPEAKING SKILLS

Karimova Dilshoda Ulugbek qizi

UzSWLU, 3rd course student

Scientific advisor: Khujaniyazova Hilola Turayevna

Senior Teacher, UzSWLU

Annotation. This study aims to analyze the impact of multi-sensory teaching approach on the progress of speaking abilities among young English language learners, specifically 4th grade students. Based on hypothesis about multi-sensory learning, the research explores how students' speaking capabilities are improved when visual, olfactory, auditory, kinesthetic, and tactile approaches are included in language acquisition. Elementary school students from Specialized schools were taught by using a multi-sensory method. The data result showed that the multi-sensory method has a strong influence on students' speaking growth, including increased vocabulary use, better pronunciation, fluency and understanding, compared to other methods. The findings suggest that for the young learner improving oral communication skills is easier if the teacher uses a multi-sensory method.

Key words: multi-sensory learning, speaking skills, visual aids, auditory input, vocabulary development, pronunciation improvement, tactile learning, teaching strategies.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot yosh ingliz tilini o'rganuvchi o'quvchilarning gapirish qobiliyatlari rivojlanishiga multi-sensory ta'lim metodining ta'sirini tahlil qilishni maqsad qilgan. Tadqiqot multi-sensory metodi haqidagi tahmin va izlanishlarga asoslanib, agar vizual, hid, eshitish, harakat va teginish usullari til o'rganish jarayoniga kiritilsa, talabalarining gapirish imkoniyatlarining yaxshilanib borishi haqida o'rganadi. Maxsus maktablardagi boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari multi-sensory metod yordamida o'qitildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, multi-sensory metod boshqa metodlar bilan solishtirilganda, o'quvchilarning gapirish rivojlanishiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi, bu esa lug'at boyligi, talaffuz, ravonlik va tushunishning yaxshilanishini o'z ichiga oladi. Natijalar shuni taklif qiladiki, agar o'qituvchi multi-sensory metodni darsda qo'llasa, yosh o'quvchilar uchun og'zaki muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish osonroq bo'ladi. Shunday qilib, multi-sensory metod to'rtinchi sinf o'quvchilari uchun darslarda qo'llanilishi uchun to'g'ri keladigan metod turi hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ko'p hissiyotli o'qitish, gapirish ko'nikmalari, ko'rgazmali vositalar, eshitish orqali axborot olish, so'z boyligini rivojlantirish, talaffuzni yaxshilash, teginish orqali o'rganish, o'qitish strategiyalari.

Introduction.

In today's rapidly developing world, the way we teach and learn languages plays an important role in shaping the minds of young people. Nailan Al Adzillina (2021) said that the phenomenon is that students have a problem in memorizing English vocabulary, as long as the teacher teaches them in a traditional way such as reading vocabulary in the textbook. The researcher supposed that while teaching students, the teachers have to use effective and beneficial methods instead of using conventional methods. One of the suitable techniques that improve early childhood oratory skills is the multi-sensory method. A multi-sensory method is a way of teaching children and enhancing their understanding by using multiple senses, such as kinesthetic, tactile, olfactory, visual and auditory. This framework can transform children's language development, helping them to learn more deeply and remember more about material. Hence, the multisensory method is a suitable method to be applied for fourth grades in the classroom.

Method

This study uses a quantitative experimental design to examine the effects of multisensory language instruction on young learners' speaking skills. Qualitative research can explain a person's experience and knowledge in depth and comprehensively (Merriam & Grenier, 2019). This study was carried out with 4th-grade students from a Specialized Education School in Uzbekistan. Totally 20 students participated and learned the topic "Wild Animals" in the lessons. The purpose of this lesson is to determine whether multisensory teaching using visual aids (pictures of animals) is more effective than common methods in developing students' oral language skills.

Table 1. Teaching Plan Using Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic Strategies

Sensory modalities	Indicators	Achievements
Visual	Students see pictures of animals	Recognize and name animals correctly
Auditory	Students hear pronunciation of new words	Pronounce words better
Kinesthetic	Students mimic animal movements	Speak with more confidence

At the end of the lessons, students completed an oral task describing wild animals using the vocabulary and structures taught during the lesson.

Results

The results revealed a clear growth in students' speaking abilities after the lesson. In the beginning of the lesson, many students could name some animals but struggled in fluency and pronunciation. After using the multi-sensory lesson, students showed noticeable improvements and significant gains in vocabulary, fluency, and confidence.

Table 2. Results of tested students

Skill area	Before (%)	After (%)
Vocabulary use	30	80
Pronunciation	40	75
Sentence fluency	25	70

Based on the results of the calculation of students' pronunciation, vocabulary use and sentence fluency with oral task in the table above, it can be seen that there was 50% growth in their speaking capability. These results are achieved by using sensory modalities.

Discussion

The resultant of this research demonstrate that the multisensory method has an enormous impact on enhancing speaking skills in young learners, particularly when engaging with the topic of "Wild Animals." By engaging visual, tactile, and kinesthetic skills in the teaching process, students were able to speak more confidently and express their ideas of the subject matter. Teachers recognize the significant benefits of multisensory learning, particularly in terms of enhanced student engagement, improved sensory development, better cognitive connections, and increased inclusivity. These insights align with existing literature that highlights the positive impacts of multisensory learning on student outcomes (Sofia Hartati, Sukrina Saida Bahri 2024). The visual element, such as using the pictures of wild animals and showing flash cards, helped students understand words with their meanings. The auditory element, helped students to learn the correct pronunciation of new words, while tactile allowed students to physically interact with the wild animals, enhancing understanding and comprehension. However, while the growth in speaking skills was successful, it is important to note that the progress may vary depending on individual student's interest, and language proficiency. These differences suggest that additional support in teaching might be needed for the students who are struggling to speak correctly and confidently.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of a multisensory approach was found to be an essential teaching strategy for improving the speaking skills of 4th grade students. By educating students through a combination of visual aids, olfactory audios and kinesthetic activities, the study showed a significant increase in students' participation, ability to express themselves and improve their vocabulary. Future research should focus on the long-term impact of multisensory techniques on language fluency and improvement in children's achievements in various spheres. Hendratno (2018) said that "In the multisensory method, the stimulus is presented in multiple modalities all at once in order to be able to overcome the differences in learning styles of children in a regular class". Overall, the multisensory approach goes beyond the common classroom methods by making learning more interactive, accessible and gratifying. Its flexibility submits that it can be successfully used in other language skills and subject spheres.

References

1. Al Adzillina, N. (2021). The impact of multisensory method on students' memorizing vocabulary at Halimah Kindergarten Prenduan Sumenep. *PANYONARA: Journal of English Education*, 3(2), 154-166 <https://ejournal.iainmadura.ac.id/index.php/panyonara/article/view/4317>
2. Merriam, S. B., & Grenier, R. S. (2019). *Qualitative Research in Practice: Examples for Discussion and Analysis*. John Wiley & Sons. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=137518>
3. Taneja, K. K., & Sankhian, A. (2019). Effect of Multi-Sensory Approach on Performance in Mathematics at Primary Level. *The Educational Beacon*, 8, 93-101. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=137518>
4. Bahri, S. S., Nurani, Y., & Hartati, S. (2024). Teachers' perspectives on multisensory learning in early childhood education: Balancing opportunities and challenges. *Linguistic and Philosophical Investigations*, 23(1), 344–358. <https://www.philolinginvestigations.com/index.php/journal/article/view/85>
5. Abdukhayotovna A. K. THE ROLE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO DEVELOP PUPILS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH CLASSES AT ACADEMIC LYCEUMS //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.
6. Rashidova, G. (2023). INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA YOZISH KO'NIKMASINI O'RGATISH JARAYONIDA ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH. *Engineering problems and innovations*.
7. Gulomova, R. (2022). AUTHENTIC MATERIALS AS A SOCIO-LINGUISTIC APPROACH. *British View*, 7(1).
8. Erdanova, Z. (2021). THE PROBLEM OF THE NORMS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(1), 74-81.
9. Erdanova, Z. (2019). Onomastic is a mirror culture. In *Science and practice: a new level of integration in the modern world* (pp. 149-152).
10. Mamatkulova, F., & Abduvaliyeva, M. (2025, April). MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 186-187).
11. Sulstonova, M., & Usmonaliyeva, M. (2024). Pragmalinguistics: exploring the social dynamics of language use. O 'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti konferensiyalari, 633-638.
12. SULTONOVA, M. (2024). On the issue of critical thinking.
13. Sulstonova, M. (2024, October). Features of Critical Thinking Skills for B1 Level Learners. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 786-790).